

The Role of Trustor Belief in Trust Repair: An Organizational Justice Perspective

Shadrack Notob Dackyirekpa¹, Timothy Masuni Nagriwum², Comfort Andoh³

¹ School of Public Affairs, University of Science and Technology, Hefei, China

² School of Finance and Economics, Jiangsu University, Jiangsu, China

³ School of Public Affairs, University of Science and Technology, Hefei, China

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Abstract: The need to investigate strategies for restoring trust has arisen from the reduction in organizational trust. There have been a shitload of studies conducted on the relationships between trust in organizations in the past, however this research explores the complex dynamics of restoring trust in organizations, emphasizing the critical roles that trustor belief and organizational justice play. The study investigates the effects of distributive, interactional, and procedural justice on trust repair while also analyzing the moderating role of trustor belief. It does this by drawing on an extensive review of relevant literature. A cross-sectional survey with 400 participants from a range of organizational roles was conducted as part of the research methodology across 60 manufacturing companies in Ghana. To confirm the validity and reliability of the constructs, a thorough analysis of the data was conducted using SPSS version 24 and Amos-SEM techniques. The results validated the significance of fairness in processes, results, and interpersonal interactions by showing a positive and significant relationship between organizational justice dimensions (procedural justice, distributive and interactional justice) and trust repair. Furthermore, the research revealed that trustor belief is a critical factor in enhancing the positive correlation between organizational justice and trust restoration. The practical and policy implications of this study emphasize the need of developing justice perceptions and trustor beliefs to support trust restoration within organizations, while the theoretical implications of this research lead to a more understanding of trust repair mechanisms. The study advocates for more investigation into other factors impacting trust restoration.

Keywords: Organizational Justice, Organizational Trust, Trust Belief, Trustor Repair.

I. INTRODUCTION

Two decades of structural reforms have brought significant changes in organizational structure, functions, processes, and behavior of employees. It has been noticed that there has been a general decline of trust in the organization among the employees due to organizational policies and structural adjustments (Singh & Srivastava, 2016). The decline in trust in organizations has necessitated the need to research into methods that are effective in repairing trust. Over the past two decades, there have been tremendous studies on trust relationships among people in organizations. These studies have exploited what causes the violation of trust among people and the efforts made by the transgressor to repair trust (Kim, Dirks, & Cooper, 2009). Several studies on the benefits of trust to organizational success such as Singh & Srivastava, (2016) argue that trust in an organization builds confidence in management and also helps in good decision-making.

Organizational trust has also been associated with positive Organizational Citizenship Behavior (Al-ali, Qalaja, & Abu-Rumman, 2019). Several studies such as Biswas et al., (2013) also suggest that trust in organizations helps promote employee engagement in the organization. Furthermore, the literature suggests that changes in organizational policies are also a known cause of the decline in trust in Organizations. The decline of confidence in management by employees due to

trust violations has stimulated studies into approaches to trust repair in organizations. Frawley & Harrison, (2016), suggest a social perspective to trust repair. In another vein, Brodt & Neville, (2013) argues a cognitive approach to repairing trust. Contemporary studies such as Tomlinson et al., (2021) have also suggested a cognitive and social approach to trust repair. Although studies like those Singh & Srivastava, (2016) mentions the role of organizational justice in organizational trust, there is a lack of literature in the area of trust repair in organization and how organizational justice is a comprehensive approach to resolving trust through an interaction with trustor belief.

According to Gill Matthew J. (2007), successful organizational relationships require trust because it is the cornerstone of cooperation, coordination, and clear communication. But trust is brittle and easily shattered, particularly when one feels mistreated or unfairly treated. When there is a breach in trust within an organization, the trustor's faith in the prospect of trust restoration becomes crucial to the healing process. From the standpoint of organizational justice, resolving trust violations and establishing a constructive and productive work environment require an awareness of the role that trustor belief plays in trust repair. In order to understand the importance of trustor belief in trust repair, this paper looks at how organizational justice principles affect trustor belief formation and the trust repair process as a whole. By exploring this subject, we can learn important things about the dynamics of mending trust and the critical role that organizational justice plays in promoting trust in the workplace. Attention has been paid to the relationship of organizational trust (OT), and its consequences on Organizational Citizenship Behavior. Again, existing literature does not provide evidence to show the extent to which procedural, distributive, and interactional justice helps in repairing violated trust and how this relationship is moderated by the action of the trustor such as belief. The study therefore seeks to suggest that organizational justice is a useful approach to repairing trust in organizations and this relationship is further strengthened by the efforts of the Trustor. This study is expected to contribute to research and practice by expanding the knowledge base of Organizational Justice and its relationship with Trust Repair and how it is impacted by trust belief.

A. Purpose of study

This study seeks to explore how trust in organizations could be repaired through organizational justice and trustor belief. The study aims to explore organizational justice as an approach to trust repair and how Trustor belief exhibits an effect on this relationship.

B. Research questions

1. How does organizational justice repair trust in organizations?
2. What is the interactional effect of trustor belief on organizational justice and trust repair?

C. Hypothesis

- H1. Perceived procedural justice is positively related to trust repair.
- H2. Interactional justice is strongly related to trust repair.
- H3. Perceived distributive justice is strongly related to trust repair
- H4. Trustor Belief exhibits a positive impact on the relationship between organizational justice and trust repair.

D. Research objectives

1. To explore how procedural justice influences trust repair.
2. To explore the relationship between distributive justice and trust repair.
3. To examine how the perceived fairness of interpersonal interaction impacts trust repair.
4. To explore the impacts of trust belief on the relationship between organizational justice and trust repair.

E. Significance of the Study

This study is expected to contribute to research and practice by expanding the knowledge base of Organizational Justice and its relationship with Trust Repair and how it is impacted by trust belief. The study will further inform management to make policies that will help in resolving violated trust in Organizations. The study will suggest cooperative methods of trust repair that include the efforts of employees, leadership, and organizational culture as a whole. The study will also serve as a basis for further discovery of organizational justice and trust.

II. REVIEW OF RELATED STUDIES

A. Trust Formation and Violation in Organizations

The concept of trust is an interesting and complex phenomenon that has been discussed by researchers and scholars from different disciplines or fields. The construct is multifaceted and has ignited discussions from psychology, sociology, management sciences, and other disciplines. Trust is a psychological state where someone (trustor) is willing to suffer vulnerability due to their belief in the integrity or competence of another (trustee). Kim et al., (2009) suggest that trust is a perceived belief in the qualities of the trustee such as competence, integrity, and benevolence. Gillespie & Dietz, (2009) also posits that trust is composed of trusting beliefs and trusting intentions. Studies have also shown that trust is borne out of gradual interpersonal relationships over time and that systematic interaction over time builds a trustor belief in the competence, integrity, and benevolence of the trustee. In organizations, employee's trust in the organization is based on their perception of fairness or organizational justice. In another vein, Singh & Srivastava, (2016) argues that organizational trust is the employees' confidence that the organization will perform an action that is meaningful or at least not detrimental to them. Faith in management, assurance about their action, honesty, and positive expectation form a few of the similar components of the construct. Studies also shows that proper organizational structures that provide emotional, psychological, social, and economic support to members of the organizations builds the trust relationship. Tomlinson & Mayer, (2009) suggests that groups that provide support to members have shown high levels of trust relationships.

Studies in organizational management have shown that perceived justice in organizations promotes organizational citizen behavior and this in turn is positively related to trust in the organization. According to Singh & Srivastava, (2016) perceived organizational justice and communication in the organization are determinants of trust. Arguably, trust in organizations is a result of confidence or belief in the support system of the organization. Research shows that the existence of a culture of trustworthiness guarantees management commitment and builds trust. Shockley et al., (2000) posits that the nature of trust relationships in organizations is reciprocal. Studies show that organizational trust is strongly related to organizational success and innovation. Violation of trust relations in the organization setting means a breakdown of the confidence invested in the organization by employees or organizational members. A sense of unfair treatment in the organization is known to negatively affect trust. Again Top, (2018) suggests poor communication between management and employees may violate trust. Trust Repair in the organization is necessary because trust is positively related to the success of the organization. In organizations, organizational justice is a useful mechanism to repair trust.

B. Theory and Hypothesis Development

Organizational Justice and Trust Repair

The concept of organizational justice has been explained by different scholars and researchers to mean different things. Whereas some scholars view it as more of a sociological concept that seeks to understand human behavior against perceived fairness in the workplace, others are of the view that it is more of a managerial concept. Some researchers argue that the concept of organizational justice is cognitive or psychological. We argue that the broad dimensions of organizational justice make it a suitable approach to repairing trust in organizations. Organizational justice explains employees' sense of fairness in an organization. The treatment an employee receives relative to others amounts to organizational justice. Studies indicate that perceived fairness is positively related to organizational citizenship behavior. Research by Singh explains that organizational justice or a perception of fairness determines and builds trust relationships between employees and employers and explains that a perceived unjust state is the ingredient that corrodes trust relationships and is capable of dissolving bonds in the workplace.

Studies by Ghosh, (2018) argue that organizational justice is based more on social consideration. They posit that human beings are social animals who wish to be accepted, respected, esteemed, and not exploited in a group, thus their perception of these things forms a sense of fairness or otherwise in an organizational setting. We believe that respect and good interaction among employees, employers, and management builds trust and thus can repair trust. Kramer & Lewicki, (2010) also argues that organizational justice is the difference between resource invested and returns made. Resources in our framework refer to liability that a trustor incurs and returns refer to what they get from a trustor such as competence, integrity, and benevolence. Studies suggest that organizational justice is appraised in three families that is distributive, procedural, and interactional justice

Procedural Justice as Trust Repair Strategy

Procedural Justice is the fairness that stems from fairness in processes, methods, procedures, and outcomes. Procedural justice enhances equilibrium in organizations and absence promotes disequilibrium. Kim et al., (2009) suggest that transgression leads to social disequilibrium and in order to repair trust there is the need for regulation and laws to restore trust. The underlining assumptions are that regulations enhance the belief of the trustor because a failure on the part of the trustee may result in punishment and this situation fosters trust repair. This position is echoed or reinforced by Ren & Gray, (2009) who posit that the belief in impersonal structures such as regulations and laws supports one's likelihood of success in trust relationships and thus promotes trust repair. Again, regulation is an indication that the trustee will bear responsibility for the offense and this further encourages the trustor to avail themselves for repair (Kim et al., 2009).

Scholars in organizational behavior argue that fairness in methods of decision-making promotes trust in management and leadership. Thus a regulation or law is strongly related to trust repair. Singh & Srivastava, (2016) suggest that fairness in procedures or methods of decision-making in organizations is strongly related to trust in management because the employees may see fair procedure as reflecting institutional. The underlining argument is that procedural justice denotes fairness in procedures, methods, or laws and the presence of regulation of law is a signal that a trustee may suffer punishment. This is positively related to trust repair and negatively related to avoidance or rejection by the trustor.

Hypothesis: Perceived procedural justice is positively related to trust repair.

Interactional justice as a social process of trust repair

Interactional justice as the name denotes refers to relations that exist between people. It also means interactional treatment and communication in respect of politeness, respect, and honesty. Interactional justice is related to a social process of trust repair because it involves quality social communication and interaction between individuals in an organization as well as the interpersonal treatment people receive (Kahkonen, 2020). Interactional justice is known to have a positive relationship with trust in the organization. The argument is that when people feel valued, respected, dignified, and fairly treated, it stimulates trust. As Ghosh, (2018) suggests, humans are social beings and wish to be accepted, respected, and esteemed and when there is the absence of these, there is a violation of trust. Thus we opine that interactional justice that includes respect, honesty, and acceptance is effective in trust repair. On the back of this, we assume that in the event of trust violation, procedural justice is significant in reviving or repairing trust. We thus propose that

Hypothesis: Interactional justice is strongly related to trust repair.

Distributive justice as a cognitive approach to trust repair

Organizational justice has been recognized as a fundamental cognitive process for building trust (Tomlinson et al., 2021). The argument is that organizational justice drives key psychological and behavioral theories. The cognitive process of trust repair posits that reparative efforts reduce the victim's stability attribution (Tomlinson & Mayer, 2009). In another vein, Tomlinson et al., (2021) argue that there is a nexus or connection between stability attribution and organizational justice (distributive justice) in the context of trust repair. Distributive justice simply means an employee's perception of fairness of outcomes (Frawley & Harrison, 2016). The central tenet is that employees look at the difference between their efforts and the returns they get to perceive fairness in an organization. The cognitive process requires that the transgressor demonstrate actions that suggest redemption or repentance (Dirks et al., 2009).

We assume that given a violated trust relationship, perceived distributive justice is an indication of goodwill thus it is an effective signal for trust repair. The basic argument is that, when there is equity in salary, wages, rewards, and outcomes, it signals to the trustor that the trustee is willing to show integrity and competence and this indication promotes trust repair. Brodt & Neville, (2013) suggest that trust is repaired when the trustor feels that they receive enough compensation for their trust and efforts. On the back of these findings, we argue that perceived procedural justice ignites a psychological state that is important in trust repair.

Hypothesis: Perceived distributive justice is strongly related to trust repair.

Trustor Actions as a Moderator

Trustor in our studies refers to the person who invests their trust in another. In our case, trustor refers to employees or members of an organization who are willing to suffer vulnerability because of their confidence in the leadership,

management, and the organization at large. Studies in trust repair have focused more on the role of the trustee (Dirks et al., 2009). A review of the literature also points to an immense contribution to the causation of trust violation. Studies like Kim et al., (2009) argue that trust repair is more effective and stronger through a negotiation of trustor and trustee efforts. In another vein, research suggests that the involvement of the trustor in the trust repair process facilitates the trust repair process. Kim et al., (2009), suggest that trustor actions such as avoidance are negatively related to trust repair. The central argument is that when the trustor attempts to avoid the relationship, they tend to perceive the efforts by the trustee to rebuild the relationship as deception tactics.

This psychological state has been proven by Kim et al., (2009) who suggest that avoidance negatively affects trust repair. Studies have also shown that mistrust communication negatively affects trust repair. However, studies have shown that when the trustor shows actions such as belief and willingness, there is strong trustor and trustee negotiation and this enhances trust repair. When a trustor shows belief, it promotes trust repair the assumption as derived from the attribution theory is that the trustor views the efforts of the trustee as a true indication of repentance and not an act of deception. When the trustor views the efforts of the trustee as genuine, it results in low levels of avoidance and resistance and this is strongly related to trust repair. We are therefore of the conviction that trustor belief is related to trust repair.

Hypothesis: Trustor Belief exhibits a positive impact on the relationship between organizational justice and trust repair.

In organizations, the efforts of the organization (trustee) such as organizational justice yield positive results toward the repair of trust. However, the efforts of the employee have a significant impact on the relationship between organizational justice and trust repair.

C. Conceptual Framework

FIGURE I: CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

Author's Construction (2023)

III. MATERIALS AND METHODS

This study employed a cross-sectional survey on trust repair within 60 companies in Ghana. The data was collected through a paid data collection service in Ghana. About 400 managers, research and development team members of the manufacturing companies, and low-level employees were included in the survey. These people reported on their demographics such as their educational background, gender, age, and work grade. The questionnaires were preceded with descriptions and instructions therefore the level of bias was reduced. All items used in this survey were selected from already validated construct items in the literature.

A. The Rationale behind the Choice of Sample

This Sample was chosen due to the fact that, these companies operate a hybrid system with people from diverse backgrounds thus supporting diversity and inclusion. Again, their activities are being influenced by interactions at different levels.

B. Measurement of Variables

Procedural Justice: Procedural justice will be measured using the seven-item formal procedures scale developed by Moorman (1991).

Distributive Justice: Distributive justice will be measured using items adapted from (Usmani & Jamal, 2013).

Interactional Justice: interactional justice will be measured using the elements recommended by (Usmani & Jamal, 2013)

Trustor Belief: Trustor Belief will be measured using the items adapted from (Reiersen, 2017).

C. Robustness Checks**Exploratory Factor Analysis / Confirmatory Factor Analysis/Construct Reliability and Validity Test**

The study employed the use of SPSS version 24 to conduct an exploratory factor analysis (EFA) and confirmatory factor analysis (CFA) of organizational justice, trustor belief, and trust repair. The reliability and validity of these variables were tested.

Model Fitness Test

A multiple regression analysis was conducted to test the fitness of this model. In order to ascertain whether a set of observed values agrees with what would be predicted by the relevant model, the Model Fitness Test is used. The test determines whether the sample data are consistent with the expected data from a population that is normally distributed.

Common Method Variance

This study employed two approaches to check for common method variance (CMV) due to the use of a single source and scale properties method of collecting data, therefore making it impossible to rule out the development of biases. The first approach following the recommendations of Kock, (2015) full collinearity test, the Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) was measured through linear regression analysis in SPSS version 24. The values of VIF were determined following a cut-off point of 10 as proposed by (O'Brien 2007). The second approach was the use of the (Tehseen, Ramayah, & Sajilan, 2017) single-factor test, evaluating the common method variance (CMV).

Descriptive Statistics and Correlation

The study reported on the descriptive statistics, mean, standard deviation, and the relationship between intellectual property management tools, open innovation and innovation performance, and the moderating role of government support.

Hypothesis Testing

A multiple regression method was used to test the hypothesized interaction through models. The study met the casual steps approach for moderation analysis. Again, the study met the methodological advice of previous studies.

Two-way Slope Test

A two-interaction slope was plotted with one standard deviation above the mean and the other below the mean. This plot was based on the interaction results. Table 1 shows a summary of the analysis

TABLE I: THE ANALYTICAL METHODS

Analysis	Thresholds	Source/Studies of:
Exploratory Factor Analysis (EFA)	>0.6 & 0.7	Hair, Babin, and Krey (2017) Fornell and Larcker (1981)
Average Variance Extracted (AVE)	> 0.7	
Composite Reliability (CR)	> 0.5	
Common Method Variance (CMV) - Harman (1967)'s single-factor test	< 50%	Harman (1967)
Variance Inflation Factor (VIF)	< 10%	Khan, Majid, Yasir, and Javed (2021)
Model fitness test using multiple regression analysis approach	R= > 0.7 R ² = > 0.5	Chin (1998) and Cohen (2002)

Hypotheses Testing - Conditions causal steps approach for mediation and moderation analysis	Each hypothesis must be tested in one model	Baron and Kenny (1986)
Two-way slope test	At one standard deviation above and below the mean	Adomako (2021)
Other analysis – correlation matrix and respondents demographics analysis		

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VI. EMPIRICAL RESULTS AND ANALYSIS

A. Descriptive Statistics

A thorough examination of descriptive statistics was carried out, which included the computation of mean, standard deviation, minimum, and maximum values for the study's construct, as meticulously presented in Table 2. Additionally, an evaluation of the dataset's normality was performed by scrutinizing skewness and kurtosis. The outcomes, diligently reported in Table 1, unequivocally confirm the absence of any significant normality issues. The recorded results, characterized by values falling within the acceptable range of +1 and -1, unmistakably indicate the data's normality, thereby allaying concerns regarding deviations from the normal distribution. This empirical observation reinforces the study's data's credibility, instilling trust in the reliability and integrity of the analytical result.

TABLE II: DESCRIPTIVE STATISTICS

Item	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation	Skewness	Kurtosis
	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic
Gender	491	1	2	1.64	0.479	-0.601	-0.645
Age	491	1	4	1.29	0.521	0.607	1.689
Religion	491	1	3	1.01	0.078	0.715	0.313
Education	491	1	4	3.67	0.782	-0.234	0.619
Marital status	491	1	4	1.71	0.454	-0.933	-1.135

Note: Gender is code as male=1, female=2, Age is coded as 20-30=1, 31-40=2, 41-50=3, 51=60=4, Religion is coded as Christian=1, Islam=2, other=3, Education is coded as none=1, Primary/Junior High=2, High school=3, Tertiary= 4

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B. Structural Model Assessment

In employing the Amos-SEM methodology for the present investigation, the initial phase involved a meticulous examination of the reliability and validity measurement models. Various statistical indices were scrutinized, including Cronbach's alpha, item loading, internal consistency, convergent reliability, discriminant validity, and confirmation of model fitness through confirmatory factor analysis. The tabulated results in Table 3 revealed that all items exhibited values within the acceptable thresholds. Notably, the primary constructs demonstrated reliability exceeding 0.7 for both Cronbach's alpha and composite reliability, while the validity criteria, particularly in terms of convergent validity, were deemed satisfactory, with average variance exceeding 0.5. This substantiates the presence of a significant correlation among the studied variables. To address issues of lower loading, items PJ1, PJ3 PJ4, and PJ5 were co-varied again items BT4, INJ4, INJ6, and TR2 were consequently excluded, leading to an enhanced discriminant validity, as corroborated by both maximum shared variance (MSV) and average variance extracted (AVE) values, as elucidated in Table 2 (MSV < AVE).

C. Robustness Check

To certify the robustness of our findings, additional scrutiny was applied through Heterotrait-Monotrait (HTMT) ratio correlations, a more conservative approach for discerning discriminant validity. It is recommended in the academic literature that HTMT ratios should be less than 0.8, and our constructs successfully adhered to this criterion. Finally, the fitness of the proposed model was validated through confirmatory factor analysis, and Table 3 delineates that all pertinent values fell within the ambit of excellence, thereby underscoring the model's robustness and reliability for further analysis.

TABLE III: RELIABILITY AND VALIDITY TEST

Variable	Factor	Cronbach	CR	AVE
Procedural justice	PJ1	0.828	0.91	0.921
	PJ2	0.809		
	PJ3	0.849		
	PJ4	0.843		
	PJ5	0.839		
Distributive justice	DJ1	0.9	0.9	0.91
	DJ2	0.865		
	DJ3	0.881		
	DJ4	0.833		
Interactional	INJ1	0.787	0.84	0.862
	INJ2	0.853		
	INJ3	0.866		
	INJ4	0.612		
	INJ5	0.765		
	INJ6	0.61		
Trustor Belief	BT1	0.889	0.905	0.919
	BT2	0.829		
	BT3	0.873		
	BT4	0.767		
Trust repair	TR1	0.904	0.86	0.876
	TR2	0.672		
	TR3	0.923		
	TR4	0.914		
	TR5	0.733		

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TABLE IV: DISCRIMINATORY VALIDITY ANALYSIS

	CR	AVE	MSV	Max R(H)	PRJ	TRUST	INT	BT	DJ
PRJ	0.921	0.7	0.197	0.921	0.837				
TRUST	0.876	0.714	0.119	1.211	0.125**	0.845			
INT	0.862	0.611	0.067	0.868	0.259***	0.01	0.782		
BT	0.919	0.792	0.197	0.924	0.444***	0.345***	0.07	0.89	
DJ	0.91	0.716	0.091	0.917	0.301***	0.03	0.07	0.112*	0.846

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TABLE V: HMTM ANALYSIS

PRJ	TRUST	INT	BT	DJ
PRJ				
TRUST	0.135			
INT	0.264	0.021		
BT	0.448	0.341	0.088	
D	0.316	0.052	0.098	0.082

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D. Model Fit Index

The authors conducted a structural equation modeling in SPSS-AMOS 24 software to test the relationship among constructs. Specifically, confirmatory factor analysis (CFA) was used to evaluate the data's fit to the model. As shown in Table 4, the majority of the measured models' GFI, AGFI, NFI, TLI, and CFI values exceeded the required value of 0.90, while chi-square statistics were less than the given cutoff point of 5.0. In a nutshell, the results in Table 4 indicated an acceptable fit with the data. Once the measurement model was deemed satisfactory, the investigator proceeded to examine the study

hypothesis in the structural model. To test the hypothesis, the investigator estimated the path coefficient, effect size, and predictive relevance while presenting the model diagnostics in Table 4. The results show an excellent CMIN/DF of 1.139 (<3) and significant CFI estimates above the acceptable range (>0.95). SRMR, RMSEA, and PClose estimates were 0.05, 0.052, and 0.34, respectively, reflecting an excellent model fitness. Notably, these model estimates were reached after excluding INJ4, INJ5, INJ6, TR2, and BT4, and covariances were observed between PJ5 and PJ4 with PJ1 and PJ3.

Table VI: Model Diagnostics Test

Measure	Estimate	Threshold	Interpretation
CMIN	311.855	--	--
DF	135	--	--
CMIN/DF	2.31	Between 1 and 3	Excellent
CFI	0.975	>0.95	Excellent
SRMR	0.05	<0.08	Excellent
RMSEA	0.052	<0.06	Excellent
PClose	0.344	>0.05	Excellent

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E. Common Method Variance

This study utilized two methods to detect the possibility of common method variance (CMV) arising from collecting data through a single source and scale properties. Such processes may lead to biases, hence the need for thorough checks. The first method adopted, as recommended by Lazaraton (2005), involved carrying out a full collinearity test by analyzing the Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) through linear regression on SPSS version 24. The second method adopted was a single-factor test carried out to evaluate the existence of common method variance (CMV).

Hypothesis Testing

The results of the study as presented in Table 5 reported a positive and significant relationship between procedural justice and trust repair at $t=2.92$ and $p=0.0041$ such that a unit increase in procedural justice will lead to a 27% increase in trust repair. Concerning the relationship between distributive justice and trust repair, the study revealed a positive and significant relationship such that an increase in distributive justice will lead to a 32% increase in trust repair. This result is unsurprising as it hypothesized that financial compensation positively influences trust repair.

Again, the results of the study suggested a positive and significant relationship between interactional justice and trust repair at $t=4.48$ and $p=0.000$ such that a unit increase in interactional justice will result in a proportional 31% increase in trust repair. Finally, the study reveals that trustor belief moderates the relationship between the dimensions of organizational justice by strengthening the positive relationship between organizational justice and trust repair.

TABLE VII: HYPOTHESIS TESTING

Hypothesis testing	Std. Beta	t-statistics	p-value	decision
H1 PJ→Trust Repair	0.2751	2.9272	.0041**	supported
H2 DJ → Trust Repair	0.32	6.214	.0000***	supported
H3 INJ→Trust Repair	0.3102	4.4819	.0000***	supported
H4 OJ*BT→OP	0.391	5.3006	.0004**	supported

Note *** indicates significance at 1% level, Critical $t=1.96$

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FIGURE II: TWO-WAY INTERACTION

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The data presented in Figure 2 indicates that trustor belief strengthens the positive relationship between organizational justice and trust repair. This follows the interpretation provided by (Aiken & West 1991).

V. RESULTS DISCUSSION

The study investigated the association between procedural justice and trust repair. Our findings revealed a positive and statistically significant relationship between these two variables. This outcome is unsurprising as it affirms the findings in prior studies (O'Brien and Tyler 2019, Tomlinson et al., 2021). Procedural justice pertains to the equity and clarity of the decision-making process. A few propositions can provide a rationale for this outcome. First, perceiving a procedure as fair increases the likelihood of individuals feeling that their opinions have been acknowledged and their concerns have been considered. By valuing and considering individuals' perspectives in the decision-making process, trust can be rebuilt. Furthermore, as posited by Lewicki and Brinsfield (2017) just procedure might contribute to the establishment of credibility and knowledge. Perceiving a procedure as fair increases individuals' faith in the competence and professionalism of those involved. This can facilitate the restoration of trust, as individuals perceive that the judgments being made are grounded on sound discernment and expertise. Furthermore, using an equitable procedure can effectively mitigate the sense of partiality or prejudice. If individuals regard a process as unfair, they may believe that judgments are influenced by personal prejudice or discrimination (Tomlinson et al., 2021). This can have particularly detrimental effects when trust has been compromised as a result of accusations of partiality or prejudice. An equitable procedure can aid in restoring confidence by showcasing that judgments are rendered based on impartial criteria rather than subjective prejudices.

Pertaining to distributive justice and trust repair, the study discovered a positive and significant relationship. This is consistent with past empirical studies such as those of Desmet, et al. (2011) and Sharma et al., (2023) who accentuated that financial compensation helps restore violated trust. One of the primary justifications for the identified positive relationship between distributive justice and trust repair lies in the cognitive processes associated with perceived fairness. When individuals perceive that the outcomes or distributions within a relationship are fair, it fosters a sense of justice and equity. Such perceptions, in turn, contribute to cognitive reconciliation, a mental process that involves individuals coming to terms with the fairness of their treatment. In the context of trust repair, this cognitive reconciliation is instrumental in alleviating the negative impact of a trust violation. Consequently, distributive justice acts as a cognitive catalyst, shaping individuals' interpretations of fairness and influencing the likelihood of successful trust repair. Again, distributive justice serves as a mechanism through which individuals assess the fairness of these exchanges. When individuals perceive that the distribution of outcomes aligns with their expectations of fairness, a reciprocal relationship is established and this is substantiated by justification in the principles of social exchange and reciprocity (Lewicki and Brinsfield 2017).

The study further discovered a positive and significant relationship between interactional justice and trust repair. This outcome is established in the studies of ALhawbani et al., (2021); O'Brien and Tyler (2019). The propositions that justify these results lie in the concepts of social identity and relational continuity. Interactional justice impacts individuals' understanding of their social identity in the organisational setting. When individuals experience a sense of respect and equitable treatment in their interpersonal interactions, it enhances their feelings of affiliation and connection to the organization. When individuals feel that they are treated with decency, respect, and honesty, it promotes favorable emotional reactions.

Finally, the study examined the moderating effect of trustor belief on the association between organizational justice and trust repair, the results revealed that organizational justice strengthens the positive relationship between organizational justice and trust repair. While there is a dearth of literature of these results, a few studies infer the role of trust belief in enabling the positive relationship between organizational justice and trust repair. For example, Tomlinson et al., (2021) mentioned the role of emotional resilience in trust repair. Again, Sharma et al., (2023) highlighted the cognitive alignment of trustor belief in trust repair. A few mechanisms substantiate the moderating role of trustor belief in organizational justice and trust repair. Trustor belief plays a crucial role in enhancing the positive connection between organizational justice and trust repair by establishing cognitive alignment. Trustor beliefs refer to the cognitive assessments made by individuals regarding the fairness and equality present in their organisational surroundings. When trustors perceive that organisational justice is maintained, it brings their cognitive perceptions in line with the principles of fairness and integrity. Again, trustor belief plays a crucial role in enhancing the positive connection between organizational justice and trust repair by establishing cognitive alignment. Trustor beliefs refer to the cognitive assessments made by individuals regarding the fairness and equality present in their organisational surroundings. When trustors perceive that organisational justice is maintained, it brings their cognitive perceptions in line with the principles of fairness and integrity.

VI. CONCLUSION AND IMPLICATION OF THE STUDY

A. Conclusion

The present study aimed to find solutions to trust repair in an era when organizational trust violation has become rampant and negatively influencing organizational performance. To do so, this study examined the relationship between organizational justice particularly procedural, distributive, and interactional justice while using trustor belief as a moderating variable. It focuses on assessing the mechanism through which fairness of procedure, outcome, and relationships help in the restoration of trust then determining the moderating effect of trustor belief on the relationship between organizational justice and trust repair.

SPSS and Amos techniques resilience for factor loading and validity concerns are utilized in this study. The test for reliability and validity revealed that constructs were in an acceptable range. The test for model fitness also reveals excellent model fitness. Finally, the SPSS regression estimator is used to assess the connections among the variables and the outcome affirms a positive and significant relationship between organizational justice and trust repair. Furthermore, trustor belief strengthened the positive relationship between organizational justice and trust repair. Based on these findings, the implications for theory, policy, and practice are emphasized.

B. Theoretical Implication

Numerous contributions from the research have an impact on the theory. First, through the integration of perspectives from organizational justice and trustor belief, the study advances our understanding of mechanisms for repairing trust within organizational settings. The synthesis of these two theoretical frameworks yields theoretical implications that illuminate the intricate relationship between trustor beliefs and perceptions of justice in the context of trust reconstruction. A vacuum in the body of literature is filled by the integration of organization justice and trustor belief, which offers a sophisticated understanding of the complex dynamics involved in trust repair. This study adds to a more thorough model of trust restoration within organizations by analyzing how justice perceptions affect trustor beliefs and, in turn, impact trust repair processes. Once more, by recognizing the complexity of justice perceptions, this study advances our knowledge of them. Recognizing that each facet of justice may play a distinct role in the process of restoring trust, this study looks at the disparate effects of distributive, procedural, and interactional justice aspects on trustor perspectives. This realization precludes the need for a more substantial and inclusive theoretical foundation by supporting the need for a more thorough approach to the study of trust repair. This encourages more research and theoretical discussion on the topic. The study also highlights the moderating effect of trustor beliefs, highlighting the significance of cognitive assessments in determining

people's propensity to reestablish trust. Comprehending the cognitive processes that underlie trustor beliefs aids in the creation of focused interventions that tackle cognitive elements essential for successful trust reconstruction.

C. Implication for Practice

Theoretical understandings gained from the integration of trustor belief in trust repair and organization justice have a number of applications for managers, practitioners, and organizational leaders. Organizations can customize protocols by pinpointing the precise justice dimension distributive, procedural, or interactional justice that has been compromised in order to gain a better understanding of the varying effects on trustor beliefs. By tackling the underlying causes of trust violations, this focused strategy increases the efficacy of trust repair programs. The emphasis on trustor beliefs can be used by practitioners to create communication strategies that specifically target cognitive appraisals. To effectively restore trust, it is imperative that the development of messages that specifically target the cognitive elements of trust sincerity, competence, and reliability be given top priority. This approach ensures that communication is in line with people's cognitive processes and increases the efficacy of the process of repairing trust. Once more, management can work with departments like human resources, organizational development, and communication to benefit from the study's interdisciplinary nature. A more complete and all-encompassing strategy for repairing trust can be achieved by incorporating organizational psychology and cognitive science insights into management procedures. This approach addresses both social and cognitive aspects of trust restoration. Finally, the results of this research can be integrated by organizations into their training and development initiatives to enhance workers' comprehension of the role that justice perceptions and trustor beliefs play in fostering a trusting workplace. The implementation of a culture that places a premium on justice, transparency, and interpersonal courtesy can effectively mitigate trust violations and bolster the general trust within an organization.

D. Implication for Policy

According to the results of this study, organizations should give priority to implementing procedural justice, distributive justice, and interactional justice to promote the restoration of trust among employees and stakeholders. Moreover, organizations must recognize that the trustors' beliefs and willingness are pivotal in enhancing the connection between organizational justice dimensions and trust repair. Hence, it is imperative to establish policies that promote the creation and execution of equitable and open policies, procedures, and interactions within organizations, with the aim of fostering and enhancing trustworthy relationships with their stakeholders.

E. Limitations of the Study

The limitation of this study includes the cross-sectional design utilized which inhibits the establishment of causal relationships amongst the variables under consideration, as well as the inability to assess the sustainability of trustor belief in the long term. Moreover, the study is confined to a specific contextual framework in Ghana, raising concerns regarding its generalizability beyond this context. To address these issues, future scholars may consider exploring the influence of a range of factors such as organizational culture, and personality traits among others. It is highly recommended the role of personality traits in the trust repair process.

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